

IDEOLOGICAL AND THEORETICAL BASICS OF PROVIDING
INFORMATION SECURITY

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Abstract: Information protection is an urgent issue of every enterprise today. The damage caused by information security incidents can have a significant impact on the fate of the organization. There are many ways and areas of information security. In this article, we talk about the information security document, which is the main document for ensuring information security in organizations.

Key words: information security, information protection, identification, law, technology, information-communication.

Ensuring information security involves the implementation of multifaceted activities of a regular and complex nature. In its implementation, it is necessary to pay special attention to the tasks set before the parties interested in information security. These various tasks can be divided into the following main groups:

1) ensuring the use of information, that is, receiving information services within a reasonable period of time and eliminating unauthorized restrictions on receiving information;

2) ensuring information integrity, that is, eliminating unauthorized modification or corruption of information;

3) ensuring information confidentiality, that is, eliminating unauthorized access to information.

Usually, the following four categories of information security subjects are distinguished, which differ from each other in terms of legal, technical, financial, organizational and other resource provision of information security:

- a whole country;
- state organizations;
- commercial structures;
- individual citizens.

It is permissible to consider the following wide range of issues covered by the above-mentioned main tasks of ensuring information security:

- confidentiality;

- integrity;
- identification;
- authentication;
- giving authority;
- control of use;
- property right;
- certification;
- signature;
- not giving up;
- write the date;
- issue a receipt for receipt;
- cancellation;
- anonymity.

The tasks listed above are described based on the needs of the current information world. Over time, some tasks may lose their relevance, and on the contrary, new tasks may appear waiting to be solved.

The governments of the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, hereinafter referred to as the "Parties", noting the significant growth in the development and introduction of new information and communication technologies and tools being formed in the global information space, technology incompatible with the tasks of ensuring international security and stability and expressing concern about the threats related to the possibility of using the tools in the civil and military spheres, giving importance to international information security as one of the main elements of the international security system, deepening the mutual trust of the Parties and developing cooperation in matters of ensuring international information security is very important believing that it is considered an important need and meets their interests, taking into account that information security is important in ensuring the basic rights and freedoms of people and citizens, taking into account the Resolution of the UN General Assembly "Advances in the field of information and telecommunications in the context of international security", to international information security They agreed to create the legal and organizational basis for the cooperation of the Parties in the field of ensuring international information security, aiming to limit threats, ensure the interests of the Parties in terms of information security, and create an international information environment characterized by peace, cooperation and compatibility.

Information protection is an urgent issue of every enterprise today. The damage caused by information security incidents can have a significant impact on the fate of

the organization. There are many ways and areas of information security. As we noted, one of the means of effective organization of information security in the organization is the introduction of an information security policy. So, what is an information security policy, how is it implemented, and what is the purpose of its implementation?

Many definitions of information security policy are given in various documents, among which a suitable definition for government agencies is as follows: information security policy is a set of measures, rules and principles that employees of an enterprise or organization follow in their daily practice to protect information resources.

In ensuring the information and psychological security of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to assume that the main legal document defining the security of the individual, society and the state is the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 13 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 439-II, adopted on December 12, 2002, "On Principles and Guarantees of Freedom of Information", which is mentioned in the first chapter of the textbook on this issue and is dedicated to the security of the individual, society and the state. In addition to Articles 14 and 15, this situation is also reflected in other legal documents. For example, articles 20, 24, 29, 31, 43, 57 and 67 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan contain opinions related to the security of the individual, society and the state. In particular, Article 20 of the Constitution states that citizens must not harm the legitimate interests, rights and freedoms of other persons, the state and society in the exercise of their rights and freedoms. Article 29 states that everyone has the right to freedom of thought, speech and belief. It is noted that everyone has the right to seek, receive and disseminate the information they want, with the exception of information directed against the current constitutional system and other restrictions established by law. At the same time, it was said that freedom of thought and expression can be limited by law only if it concerns state secrets and other secrets.

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